

Management

INCREASING JOB PROSPECTS IN THE FIELD OF INDUSTRIAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The students are turning down the engineering courses which result in lakhs of seats remaining vacant every year whereas the trend of ITI education is increasing. The reason behind the huge demand for ITI students as there is a great demand from industry for electrician, fitter, machinist, turners and mechanics in diesel as well as in motor. All these courses are offered at ITI. A few years back, the situation was different as students were attracted to engineering and management courses and very few people used to join ITI branch. Due to economical shut down the opportunities in Engineering and Management branches saw a dip.

Keywords: Job Prospects; Engineering Courses.

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1. Introduction

At present everybody wants quick jobs within short period of time, the ITI is the best option as compare to the fees of engineering and management, the fees are not that big and even students from economically weaker sections who want to pursue their career in technical field, drifting toward ITI courses. There are more than 50 subjects in which the training is offered to the students in 2 year course and syllabus is designed on the basis of industry requirement. Even the industries too prefer students from ITI as compare to engineering students they do not have to offer big salary package to ITI trainees.

The reason why students prefer ITI courses is that those who want to go for engineering, they can get admission to second year after completing ITI and they do not have to clear class XII exam. Now a class VIII pass out would be able to get a class X certificate after 2 years in ITI, and 2 more years of training will make him eligible to acquire class XII certificate. The students will also be eligible for further admission in college like any other regular student. Such

certificates will be honored by all educational institutes for further opportunities for higher studies.

In ITI focus is towards imparting 70% skills and 30% theory. Candidates after completing ITI have both academic and job oriented prospects to continue with. Aspirants after passing ITI can go for specialized short term courses in Advanced Training Institute (ATI). ITI trained candidates can apply for higher studies like Diploma in Engineering. In the month of June 2017, 588 posts by east coast railway, 4110 posts by ordnance factory board, 2365 posts by MP professional examination board (VYAPAM), 2946 posts by CRPF, 2459 by HSSC and more than 1500 posts by other govt. recruitment agencies are notified by govt. for ITI qualified candidates.

Industrial training institutes provide technical education in various trades under Directorate General of Employment and Training. Generally a 10th class passed person is eligible for admission in ITI. The main objective of opening of ITI is to provide technical manpower to various industries. To make ITI more qualitative, ITI instructors are trained under the craft instructor training scheme (CIT) in the field institute of DGT. Field institutes of DGT have facility for imparting the instructor training in 27 trades. The gross capacity of these institutes is around 1600 instructors per annum.

2. Objective of Study

- To find student's interest to join ITI
- To find status of job selection of ITI qualified students

3. Hypothesis

- There is no significant interest of students to join ITI course.
- There is no significant status of selection of ITI qualified candidates.

4. Methodology

Descriptive survey method was adopted for study. 2 samples of 500 students were randomly selected having 50% male and female in equal ratio of rural and urban. In sample 1, students of class 12th were interviewed to know course of their interest and future prospects. Sample 2 consists of ITI qualified candidates. They were asked for job status. Collected data was tabulated, converted into percentage and comparatively analyzed.

5. Finding and Analysis

Table 1: Status of ITI in India

Detail	Category	No.
No. of ITI	Govt.	2284
	Pvt.	9680
No. of Trades	Engineering	73

	Non Engineering	48
	For Visually Impaired	5
Total No. of Seats in ITI		12,96,748
Total No. of Trainees		11,65,996
Seat Utilization		89.92%

*Source: www.dget.nic.in

Chart 1: Status of No. of Students interested in ITI courses

Table 2: Status of No. of Students interested in ITI courses

Subject Stream	No. of Students %			
	ITI interested		Other Course interested	
	Engineering Trade	Non Engineering Trade	Professional Course	General Course
Math Science	46	15	14	25
Bio Science	24	11	23	44
Commerce	16	12	26	46
Arts	15	11	16	58

Chart 2: Status of Job Selection of ITI Qualified (Engineering Trade) Trainees

Table 3: Status of Job Selection of ITI Qualified (Engineering Trade) Trainees

Engineering Trade	No. of ITI Qualified Candidates Selected For Job %		
	Govt. Sector	Private Sector	Self Employment
Electrician	14	71	12
Fitter	12	68	8
Diesel Mechanic	11	66	11
Welder	9	55	17
Plumber	9	57	14

Chart 3: Status of Job Selection of ITI Qualified (Non Engineering Trade) Trainees

Table 4: Status of Job Selection of ITI Qualified (Non Engineering Trade) Trainees

Non Engineering Trade	No. of ITI Qualified Candidates Selected For Job %		
	Govt. Sector	Private Sector	Self Employment
COPA	16	71	6
Stenographer and Secretarial Assistant	11	57	2
Dress Making	4	54	23
Interior Decoration & Designing	3	39	21
Health Sanitary Inspector	9	68	3

Student interest data shows that math science back ground students have highest interest in engineering trades i.e., 46% and bio science student's 24%. 16% commerce and 15% arts stream student's shows inclination towards ITI engineering courses. Student's interest for non-engineering course is low. Hence, hypothesis 1 there is no significant interest of students to join ITI course is rejected.

Job selection data of ITI students show that in govt. sector selection % is 14%, 12%, 11% and 9% respectively for electrician, fitter, diesel mechanic, welder and plumber while in private sector is 71%, 68%, 66%, 55% and 57% respectively, self-employment % is 12%, 8%, 11% 17% and 14% respectively.

Among non-engineering trades, COPA trade is successful trade, its 16% candidates are selected in govt. sector, 71% in private sector and 6% in self-employment. For stenographer trade job selection status is 11%, 57% and 2% respectively. Dress making trade indicates selection % as 4% in govt. sector, 54% in private and 23% are self-employed. For Interior decoration and sanitary health inspector selection % is 3%, 9% in govt. sector, 39%, 68% in private sector and 21%, 3% as self-employment. Thus hypothesis 2 there is no significant status of selection of ITI qualified candidates is rejected.

6. Conclusion

ITI play a vital role in economy of the country especially for providing skilled man power. The courses in the ITI are designed in such a way they can prove helpful to impart basic skills in the trade specified. Govt. of India, public sector units and state govt. organizations are looking for young and experienced ITI holding candidates for the recruitment of various trade vacancies for both engineering and non-engineering trades. ITI passed candidates can set their own business like they can open winding shop, motor garage, electrical equipment repairing workshop, AC repairing, machine repairing, mechanical workshop etc. ITI qualified students have bright opportunities in foreign countries also.

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